

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING UNDERWRITING PROCESSES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

Bobojonov Khursand Kadamovich

“Ipoteka-bank” JSCIB OTP group, Credit Approval Department, Senior Underwriter-Manager, Retail and Small-Medium Business Underwriting Department. E-mail: khursandbek0204@mail.ru
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We know that the fiscal, innovative and investment policies of each country serve as the main factor in achieving stable growth rates of the country's economy. In recent years, structural changes in the economy of our country and further increase of investment standards, strengthening of its stability and strengthening of macroeconomic stability have been given special importance.

If we pay attention to the activity of commercial banks, commercial banks participate in the stock market not only as issuers and investors, but also as financial intermediaries. In this way, commercial banks, in addition to directing their savings to the stock market, help to actively attract and redistribute the funds of the population and various investors to the stock market. "Banks, insurance companies and non-state pension funds, which are highlighted as strong institutional investors, offer relevant financial services, and also influence the investment environment in the country, are the main participants in investment activity". Therefore, increasing the activity of commercial banks in the stock market becomes relevant not only in national practice, but also in international practice. In particular, the existence of issues such as increasing the investment attractiveness of commercial banks through their participation in the stock market, regulating relations with investors in their dividend policy and interest policy, improving the intermediary activity of commercial banks, in particular, the underwriting activity, requires the conduct of a number of scientific studies in this regard. is enough.

"In the United States, even investment banks are prohibited from investing in corporate securities and mediating their placement. On the other hand, in Europe, on the contrary, restrictions on universal banks' activity in the securities market are not put forward in the legislation. And on this basis, attention will be paid to business development."

"Participation of banks in the bond market had a positive effect on the activity of banks by improving the structure of the banks' portfolio and reducing

the risks of the banks." These aspects reveal the advantages of banks' participation in the stock market.

It mediates between companies and investors who want to raise capital through the process of public placement of shares through an underwriting service. Manages mergers and acquisitions (M&A) processes and acts as an advisor to participants in this process. In addition, it participates in the trading of securities in the secondary market and helps investors participating in securities trading in making investment decisions. It also serves as an asset manager in managing investments for a wide range of investors, including institutions and individuals.

Unlike the banks of developed countries, commercial banks of our republic do not have the opportunity to ensure their current liquidity at the expense of government securities. The reason for this is that, firstly, the volume of issuance of Government securities is small, and secondly, in the practice of our republic, there are no securities whose payment is guaranteed by the Government.

It should be admitted that in connection with the liberalization of the currency policy, from September 5, 2020, the nominal exchange rate of the soum against the US dollar almost doubled, that is, the rate of depreciation of the soum against the US dollar was almost 2 times. This resulted in a high rate of depreciation, which led to a decrease in the real value of investments in securities denominated in the national currency. As a result, the investment attractiveness of securities denominated in national currency by residents has decreased.

Figure 1. The world shows that substantial shakeups in top municipal underwriters of 2023

The changes reflect a year of layoffs at several Wall Street firms, including UBS's negotiated underwriting business and Citigroup's decision in October to exit its muni underwriting business in November.

The industry overcame its second straight year of volume declines, which fueled competition for fewer deals and tightened underwriting spreads. Depreciating bonds put balance sheets in doubt. Another pressure point was the March banking crisis and political dynamics in Texas, one of the market's largest issuers and formerly one of Citi's top clients.

The top underwriters accounted for \$362.847 billion in 7,268 transactions in 2023, and \$359.846 billion in 7,906 transactions in 2022.

In conclusion, we can say that now commercial banks are required to conduct extensive research of investment opportunities in economic sectors and business sectors, and based on their results, direct investments in sectors and business sectors. The incentives created by our government make it possible to further develop the investment activities of banks. The reason is that banks' investments in liquid securities play a major role in performing a number of important functions in the bank's internal management and improving its operations. These securities, unlike loans, constitute an additional source of income. This is very important for banks and shareholders. Also, this operation, as mentioned above, ensures that the bank maintains its liquidity and meets the bank's demand for financial resources in a timely manner. Another feature of this operation is that it serves to reduce the bank's tax liabilities by investing in tax-exempt securities.

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